

Survey report on Activity 4.1.1

Identification of possible biological topics/quantities that require metrological sound measurements

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Purpose and methodology

This survey aimed to identify the most relevant biological quantities requiring metrologically sound measurements for future research. An online questionnaire was distributed to activity participants, comprising 24 closed-ended questions rated on a 1-to-5 importance scale and 14 open-ended questions, resulting in 29 responses.

Quantitative data from the scaled questions was analyzed to determine which quantities participants consider most critical for their models or systems. Qualitative responses were grouped and synthesized to capture recurring themes and representative ideas. This combined approach provides a comprehensive view of current practices, emerging needs, and priorities for protocol development.

Question 1 - How important is it to measure this quantity in your model or system?

Please rate the importance from 1 to 5 (1 for not very important, 5 to very important). It is essential to quantify all items on the list.

Results

These answers indicate that biocompatibility is considered the most critical parameter, with the highest proportion of responses rating it as “the most important.” Sterilization and compatibility with incubator conditions also rank very highly, reflecting their essential role in maintaining system integrity and safety.

Material properties such as transparency and fluorescence are moderately important, while factors related to cell behavior—like cell adhesion, apoptosis, and live-dead staining—show mixed importance, generally leaning toward moderate to high relevance.

In contrast, confluency and soluble markers are viewed as less critical compared to structural and compatibility considerations.

Question 2 - How much need is there for new protocols to measure this quantity in a microfluidic environment?

Please rate the need from 1 to 5 (1 for not very important, 5 to very important).

Results

The responses show that the greatest need for new protocols in microfluidic environments is biocompatibility, which received the highest ratings (levels 4 and 5). These findings suggest that biological compatibility is a major challenge in microfluidic systems.

There is also a notable demand for improved methods addressing cell-layer integrity, such as leakage/permeability, cell adhesion, and soluble markers, indicating difficulties in maintaining biological functionality under microfluidic conditions.

In contrast, parameters like confluency and live/dead staining were mostly rated as low priority (levels 1 and 2), implying that existing protocols are generally adequate for these measurements.

Overall, the data highlights a strong need for innovation in protocols related to material properties and cell interactions within microfluidic environments.

Question 2.1 - Which protocol do you currently use to measure this quantity?

Please provide a reference (such as ISO, EN or other standards, methods' name, scientific paper, etc).

Results

The chart shows that microscopy and image analysis are the most commonly used protocols for measuring confluency, accounting for 38% of responses. The following is a diverse group categorized as others (29%), which includes various references to scientific methodologies and other standardized methods.

Smaller shares (around 7% each) are seen for visual/electrical methods, electrical measurements, use of Cellpose software, and cases where no formal protocol is used, relying instead on visual inspection.

Overall, the data suggests that while microscopy remains the dominant method, there is a significant reliance on alternative and non-standardized approaches, revealing high variability of methodologies.

Live-dead staining

The majority of respondents (57%) rely on visual assessment for live-dead staining, making it the most common approach. Manufacturer protocols account for 36%, showing that standardized methods provided by kit suppliers are also widely used. A small proportion (7%) reported using other protocols.

Overall, the data highlights a strong preference for simple visual evaluation, with manufacturer guidelines serving as the main structured method.

Soluble markers

The highest percentage was 20% of the participants referred using specific methodologies and manufactures protocols. Different methods share similar lower levels of use, including

luminescence assay, enzyme immunoassay, colorimetric assay, and fluorescent redox assay, each accounting for about 13%. Smaller proportions (7% each) are reported for visual analysis, Alamar blue assays, and exosome-based approaches, indicating these are less common. Overall, the data suggests a diverse range of protocols is employed, with no single method dominating.

Apoptosis

The chart shows that Caspase assay is the most commonly used protocol for measuring apoptosis, accounting for 30% of responses. Fluorescent staining assays follows with 20%, making it another widely adopted method. Several other techniques, including cell proliferation assay, Annexin V assay, enzyme immunoassay, reference methods, and tunnel assay, each represent 10%, indicating a diverse but less frequent use of these approaches.

Overall, the data suggests that while caspase and fluorescent staining assays dominate, there is considerable variability in protocols, reflecting the complexity of its measurement.

Chemical ad/absorption

Reference methods are the most commonly used protocol for measuring chemical adsorption/absorption, accounting for 50% of responses. The remaining answers are evenly split between mass balance and absorbance/fluorescence techniques, each representing 25%.

Cell adhesion

38% of responses referred the use of reference methods for measuring cell adhesion. All other approaches—RTCA, fluorescent staining, visual analysis, SEM, and laminar flow—are equally represented at 13% each, indicating a wide diversity of techniques. This shows the high variability in practices for assessing cell adhesion.

Leakage/permeability of cell layer

Permeability assays are the most commonly used protocol for measuring leakage or permeability of the cell layer, accounting for 31% of responses. Fluorescent staining and electrical resistance or permeability assay each represent 23%, indicating these are also widely adopted methods. Smaller shares (8% each) are reported for visual analysis, and electrical methods.

Biocompatibility

Previously mentioned viability assays and ISO-based protocols are the most commonly used methods for assessing biocompatibility, each accounting for 33% of responses. Other approaches, including enzyme immunoassay, reference methods, and cell count, are less frequently used, each representing 11%. Overall, the data highlights a preference for established and widely recognized protocols to ensure reliable biocompatibility evaluation.

Sterilization

The most used protocols for sterilization are mainly divided between reference methods and UV/Ethanol treatments, each accounting for 38% of responses. Microbiology assays represent the remaining 25%, indicating biological testing to confirm sterility. Overall, the data suggests that most users rely on standardized or chemical-based approaches, while microbiological verification is less common, possibly due to its complexity and resource requirements.

Compatibility with incubator conditions

No specific protocols were referred by the participants.

Fluorescence of device material

Among the protocols used to measure the fluorescence of device material, spectrophotometry, microscopy, and a combination of both methodologies were referred, making these two the main protocols currently used by the participants.

Transparency of device material

The chart shows that visual analysis is the most commonly used protocol for measuring the transparency of device material, accounting for 43% of responses. Reference methods follow with 29%, while spectrophotometry and combined microscopy or spectrophotometry each representing 14%. This distribution indicates a strong reliance on simple visual inspection, with fewer users employing quantitative optical techniques.

Overall, the data suggests that transparency assessment is often performed using basic observational methods rather than standardized or instrument-based protocols.

Question 3 - Are there any other quantities that you use to characterize your model or system that were not presented in this survey?

Results

Other quantities used for characterization

Respondents identified several additional quantities used to characterize their models or systems beyond those listed in the survey.

The most frequently mentioned was oxygen consumption (25%). Other parameters include transporter activity in kidney, functional tests in heart, biomarker detection, metabolic rate, membrane mechanical properties, cell infiltration, microplate reader reliability, cell count, and extracellular acidification.

This suggests that characterization often extends to physiological and metabolic aspects, as well as mechanical and analytical reliability factors, highlighting the diversity of requirements for comprehensive assessment of the microfluidic system.

Question 4 - Are there any other quantities that you would like to see reported by component and material suppliers besides the ones addressed in this survey?

Results

Other quantities of interest

The chart reveals a diversity of additional quantities that participants would like to measure beyond those listed in the survey. Each parameter — oxidative stress, EV secretion, limits of measurement for reliability, surface roughness/biofilm adhesion, metabolic activity, oxygen concentration, composition of cell culture medium, and reusability of components — accounts for 13%, showing equal importance for the participants.

Final comments

In conclusion, the survey results revealed the need to develop robust protocols for material properties and cell-interaction measurements in microfluidic environments, while ensuring harmonization of existing practices.

The additional quantities identified point toward a broader, multidimensional approach to characterization, encompassing functional, structural, and sustainability aspects.